

Contraceptive Challenges in Developing Countries: Bridging the Gap Between Availability and Accessibility

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ABSTRACT

Contraception is the intentional use of preventive strategies to delay childbearing or prevent unwanted pregnancies. Contraception as per law, should be easily available, easily accessible and without side effects for the user. India has recently became the world's largest populous country, bypassing China, and currently we have a population of roughly around 140 crores. Thus, the importance of contraceptive use must be promoted and taught at every level of society. Various contraceptive methods are available for reproductive couples but, the lack of knowledge, myths regarding the side effects of contraception, difficult user manual, all hinder the proper use of contraceptive methods in the Indian population. In this study, we will discuss and highlight the challenges faced by fertile couples for availing contraceptive resources and having a healthy and safe family planning approach.

INTRODUCTION

Developing countries are often characterised by excessive birth rates and explosive population growth . One of the major reasons considered for such high birth rates in developing countries is unmet need for family planning (FP), which is also defined as the proportion of women willing to delay the childbirth, but are not using any method of contraception due to lack of awareness or unavailability, has been one of the main concerns for reproductive health policy makers and family planning programs in LMICs ^[1]. Women and girls in many developing countries still have the inhibition in getting access to modern and better formulated methods of contraceptives. This can occur due to lack of education among the female population, lack of skilled and trained contraceptive providers in the regions and poor availability of the contraceptives supplies ^[2]. Contraceptive methods can be any process which prevents a fertile couple from getting pregnant like medications, medical devices, sexual practices, chemical or surgical procedures ^[3]. An effective contraceptive method is the one which - is easily available, easily accessible, cost-effective, free from side effects, easy to use. There are various contraceptive methods available for the Indian sub-population like - barrier methods (male and female condoms), devices (Intrauterine contraceptive device), medications (I-pill, emergency contraceptive pill, injections), sexual practices (coitus interruptus, rhythm method).

As per the Family planning summit 2012 global partnership, it has been estimated to add 120 million females into the modern contraceptive technique by 2020 ^[4].

According to DHS report 2014, there are around 225 million females with unmet contraceptive demands of which 125 million have no contraceptive method access and 100 million follow traditional ways of contraception ^[5]. Based on studies, 1 in every 5 married women have unmet needs of contraception and thus, family planning (government initiative) has a major role in helping reproductive couples to choose the contraceptive way and have smaller families, with easy accessibility to contraceptive methods. In the last three decades, the prevalence for contraception has seen a rise from about 10% to approximately 60% in many developing countries, but the challenge of unwanted births is still faced in these countries as about 1 in 4 births in developing countries are unwanted ^[6]. Therefore the need for family planning for bridging the gap between the availability and use of contraception was well known to the policy makers of our country and hence, India was the first country to initiate family planning measures in 1952. Unplanned pregnancies among various different age groups including the adolescent age group represents an important challenge in developed as well as developing countries. In order to address the issue of unplanned pregnancies, countries around the globe have implemented various strategies which include providing access to various methods of contraception, education about sexual health to girls and women, risk assessment of unprotected coitus and knowledge for various sexually transmitted diseases ^[7]. UNFPA also focuses on working closely with the governments of various developing countries in order to increase the access to family planning programmes among the

population. This study focuses on various challenges faced by developing countries as well as the solutions for the contraceptive needs.

Methodology

This study is a retrospective, observational study in which, data already available, were analyzed and reported in this study. To conduct this review, a comprehensive literature search was performed using several electronic databases, including pubmed and Official websites like the national family health survey (NFHS), along with international official website for gathering data (2015-21). The search strategy involved the use of relevant keywords like family programming, developing countries, third world countries, contraception and associated concepts.

BACKGROUND

One of the major problems the world is facing is the exponential growth of the population and usually, the third world countries are identified with higher growth of population over a short period of time. Exponential growth in the population of the developing countries has led to high demand for resources, increased competition among various sectors of jobs, over usage of the existing natural resources and overcrowding. Overpopulation is not only a threat to our environmental resources but also to the already existing population as it can also cause enormous unemployment among them and due to unemployment, some sections of population resort to a life of crime which can lead to unharmony in some sections of the society^[8]. In order to limit high population growth across different parts of the world, various family programming initiatives are taken by the government as well as the WHO but the challenges remain the same due to the unmet need of contraceptives in various developing countries. There are various reasons for the unmet need of contraception which include - lack of education in the population, difficulty in availability of the contraception, and generic objection to preventing child bearing^[9]. The women's unmet need for contraception throws light on the gap seen in between women's fertility intentions and the lack of availability of contraceptive methods^[10]. By educating the female population of the third world countries, one can help them to avoid the chances of unplanned pregnancies and integrating such programs will not only help in reducing the population of the country but will also reduce unwanted child births, life threatening abortions and will also help in improving the health of the reproductive female population and child^[11]. The abstract of unmet need for contraception usage is often dissipated and misinterpreted. Surveys conducted in the developing regions usually estimate the unmet need of contraceptive methods among the female population. It represents the section of population who want to get access to various contraceptive methods according to their preferences but due to the shortage of different contraceptive devices in their regions are not able to do so^[12]. The objective of this study is to highlight the topic of contraceptive challenges in developing countries around the globe and also focus on bridging the gap between the access and availability among different sections of the society.

Contraceptive Availability in Developing Countries

Overview of contraceptive methods:

The avoidance of unwanted and clinically unsafe pregnancies for women remains a vital part for improving maternal and child healthcare. The use of contraception not only helps in controlling the population of the country but it also helps in preventing the spread of Sexually Transmitted Diseases that include gonorrhea, genital herpes, human papillomavirus infection, chlamydia, HIV/AIDS and syphilis. Sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) are one of chief causes of poor health in women, their sexual partners and children [13]. It is also characterised as one of the important parts in the clinical practice of medicine. The categorization of different contraceptive products can be done by their hormonal content and the method of usage [14].

Condoms are used to avoid the entry of semen , fluids of the body and the organisms which can cause STDs except the fragments of hepatitis B. The effectiveness of Condoms in avoiding the spread of STDs and various infections is only 50% [15]. The cervical cap and the diaphragm are the contraceptive methods that are used in the vagina to prevent pregnancy by blocking the cervix . The cervical cap is a cup shaped structure which is soft and small in structure , this device completely covers the cervix in order to avoid the entry of sperms . The diaphragm is usually placed in the vagina in such a way that the dome of the device completely covers the cervix blocking the entry of sperm [16]. Intrauterine devices (IUDs) are one of the most effective forms of contraception available. The two types of IUDs that are presently used in the United States, includes the copper-containing IUD and levonorgestrel-containing IUD, which have similar rates of preventing pregnancy, with failure rates of 0.08% and 0.02%, respectively.

Another method of contraception is oral contraceptives. Usually these oral contraceptive pills are a combination of progesterone and estrogen , since these are formulated with two hormones which help in preventing pregnancy these are also called birth control pills or combination pills as they contain both estrogen and progesterone . The dosage of these pills vary for different pills as the amount of two hormones used in different pills is different . However, all the combination pills are consumed on 21 or 22 days per menstrual cycle .

Challenges in the availability of contraceptives

Developing countries across the globe usually face challenges in getting access to different methods of contraception. In most of the developing countries the availability of choice in between different methods of contraception is very low. Different sections of the population are unable to get access to their preferable choice of contraception due to its unavailability. The inefficacy in the working of the supply chain system produces a huge impact on the distribution of different methods of contraception especially in the rural areas of various developing countries, due to the inefficient working of the supply chain many family planning programmes fail in a lot of regions ^[17]. Most of the family planning programmes introduced by the government to raise awareness about different methods of contraception but due to weak foundation of the policy which include lack of skilled work force and regulatory norms these programmes usually fail. Various family planning programmes also fails due to lack of funding by the government on these policies, this causes hindrance in achieving the goal of providing knowledge about contraception to different sections of the populations.

Contraceptive Access in Developing Countries

Socio-cultural factors affecting access to contraceptives

In many developing countries there is a prevalence of patriarchy among many families . Often the husband influences the healthcare decisions and one such decision taken is use of contraception. Even literate women who want to use contraceptives in order to avoid childbearing or space between the child birth are not able to do so due the influence of husband's decision on family planning and usage of contraception ^[18]. For instance, in a study from Pakistan the women usually don't hold any power in the family planning decisions, their preferences and attitude towards contraception is governed by their husband ^[19]. Similar findings were reported by a 2014 study conducted in Uganda where it was found that it was the husband who made primary decisions about the usage of contraceptives during coitus, however this is often viewed as an obstacle for women who want to use contraception for family planning ^[20]. Lack of correct knowledge about contraception also creates stigma and misconceptions among the population. It not only creates obstacles in the family planning programmes among different families but also creates a negative impact on the society level due to which there are higher population growth rates. Another challenge in accessing contraceptives includes religious sentiments of the population. The Roman catholic church disallowed the use of contraception as it considered it a sin against nature. However some protestant religious groups have permitted the use of contraception. Children are considered as gifts from Allah according to Islamic law. However some muslims believe that one must produce many children. According to Hinduism and Buddhism there is no restriction on the usage of contraception ^[21].

Barriers to accessing contraception

Many cultural and familial barriers to family planning usually influence a woman's decision to use contraception. Barriers to accessing contraception also include lack of knowledge , health concerns , limited availability of contraception , high cost of contraception and various cultural and personal objections which include the socioeconomic status of the family , awareness about the use of contraceptives and also its disadvantages ^[22]. One barrier to accessing contraception is due to geographical barriers as the majority of the population in third world countries are located in the rural areas. Due to this geographical barrier within the country it is difficult for families to adopt family planning programmes. Low income developing countries usually have high rates of unintended pregnancies. Many families living in low income developing countries have a poor socioeconomic status due to which they are not able to incorporate family planning programmes as it is not affordable for them . Therefore it is important for the providers to not only make different methods of contraception accessible and affordable in different regions of the country. Third world countries are also characterised by lack of an organised healthcare system, due to limited healthcare facilities and infrastructure it is often an obstacle for families to know about the existing methods of avoiding pregnancy and incorporating family planning programming at an early stage .

Contraceptive Programs and Initiatives

Due to the high population in the developing countries, it is important for the policy makers and government to introduce programmes and initiatives to not only control the population but to also preserve the existing natural resources for the future generation. For instance , in April 1972, India introduced national population policy. The

important features of this policy included increasing the marriage age for women from 15 years to 18 years and for men from 18 years to 21 years, focusing on the education of women and girls, introduction of population control programmes in rural India and increasing monetary compensation for sterilization ^[23]. In order to limit the growth of population in India the policy makers have reviewed and evaluated the 1951 - 5 year plan. However the family planning programmes haven't been a great success due to no improvement in people's attitude towards the usage of contraception. Using contraception and incorporating family planning is self generating ^[24]. Another instance, in the 1950s and 1960's Pakistani government and private institutions introduced several family planning programmes. But even after 50 years, Pakistan still adds four million people to its population each year . The family planning programmes also failed in reducing the number of children per family. A Pakistani family has an average of six children and this number has barely fallen since the 1960s ^[25]. The above mentioned initiatives haven't proved to create a massive difference in the control of the population. But another developing country which was able to spread the knowledge about contraceptives and help its population to use contraceptives was Bangladesh. In 1977 in the Matlab's sub-district the International Centre for Diarrheal Disease Research, Bangladesh launched a programme in which the empowered women were assigned the task to educate other women about the usage of contraception. Skilled women force went door to door every month in an unobtrusive way to provide the access of contraception to women this included birth control and injections. By 1982, this programme added vaccinations as well in order to provide health care facilities to the families ^[26]. This also suggests that providing employment opportunities to skilled women can help in not only improving the financial status of women but also helps in increasing awareness among different women belonging from different communities and therefore making the social boundaries less rigid for other women ^[27]. The case of Matlab's sub district of Bangladesh highlights the participation of a skilled female workforce in educating other women about family planning . It also throws light on the importance of providing education to the rural population. In addition to Bangladesh , many other south Asian countries including Bhutan, Indonesia, Nepal and Sri Lanka where seven methods of contraception are available accounts for a higher modern contraceptive prevalence rate (mCPR) than India (as in 2015) where only 5 methods of contraception are available ^[28]. The case of other south asian countries shows that increasing the methods of contraception can lead to increasing the rate of usage of contraception among the population.

Role of stakeholders in bridging the gap

Several stakeholders including the government of the country, policy makers, non governmental organizations and the private sectors play an important role in bridging the gap between availability and accessibility . The government of India has introduced various family planning programmes . The government of India at the London summit held in 2012 on family planning made a global commitment to provide the services of family planning to an additional 48 million users by 2020 ^[29]. Government has also made consistent efforts to provide education to the population about contraception. The Non governmental organisations help provide aid to the already existing health care policies as they work on meeting the needs of low income population at a local level by understanding their socioeconomic condition as well their cultural background , which leads to active participation from the population ^[30]. The NGOs

also play an essential role in educating the population living in the slum areas about the non surgical methods of contraception , they also distribute various contraceptive devices for the usage . Many NGOs also collaborate with INDIAN RED CROSS society , NSS, NCC, scouts to organise awareness camps. The United Nation Population Fund also focuses on the introduction of effective family planning programmes and the stable supply of good quality contraceptives which can strengthen the already existing family planning programmes and health care system of the country ^[31]. Since the low income countries have limited funds a coordinated and continued approach from the private sectors which include both private nonprofit sectors and private commercial sectors is essential as it can help in meeting the demands of contraception in the population ^[32]. The approach followed by these sectors is known as “total market approach” which emphasizes on the sustainable market growth of family planning . The private sectors have better resources and infrastructure and can target a wider audience through various means which include advertisements and awareness camps ^[33]. In order to bridge the gap between availability and accessibility it is also important to take help from healthcare providers and professionals as they can help in recommending the best method of contraception based on the couple’s preferences and needs. To bridge the gap completely it is important for every sector to work together and efficiently.

Addressing contraceptive challenges : Recommendations

In order to address contraceptive challenges it is important to address the existing challenges . One of the best ways to control the growth of population in developing countries can be done by combining political education and effective economic measures which includes coordinated employment ,introduction of sex education in schools and introduction of effective policies by the government ^[34]. Government can introduce policies which aim at the family welfare programmes which should make family planning services accessible at village level. The government also needs to introduce small family norms and focus on improvement of the socioeconomic conditions of the families ^[35]. Other measures which can be introduced include collaborative efforts of the population and the government along with the partnership of various NGOs and healthcare professionals .

RESULTS

The national family health survey (NFHS-5) data has shown the decline in unmet needs of contraception from 13% (NFHS-4) to 9%. The contraceptive prevalence ratio (CPR) has significantly increased from 53% to 67 % in NFHS-5. Use of modern contraceptive techniques has increased in almost all union territories and among city population, but still lacking behind in rural backgrounds.

There is still unmet needs of contraception widely because of :

A. Lack of Knowledge : The most widely encountered reason for contraceptive challenge is poor knowledge among fertile couples. Poor parental education for contraception is a major drawback in lack and improper use of contraceptive methods.

- B. Cultural beliefs:** Improper reviews by people in the society plays a major roadblock for proper contraception usage by couples in the community.
- C. More demand, less economical :** In some cases, there have been instances when there is low usage of contraception due to poor quality and cheaper products, and thus, increase in negligence for the products. Good products come with an increase in price and thus, avoidance by the general population.

The challenges still remains high for providing the best contraceptive methods to the eligible couples and they are enlisted below -

- **Improvement of delivery of service system :** The delivery of services for reaching the younger population should be strengthened as poor service availability will lead to decreased utilization of the modern contraceptive methods.
- **Financial support by government:** Government organizations plays important role in strengthening the family planning programs at multiple levels like, funding for contraceptives, educating young couples and school sex education. Poor government interest in these sections will lead to poor contraceptive knowledge and thus, boom to the population leading to more maternal deaths, unwanted pregnancy, increased infant mortality rates.

CONCLUSION

The contraceptive challenge is a major issue in developing countries and the gap for bridging it, based on our study, is proper female education, government interference in providing good and affordable contraceptive options to the young fertile couple and improving school sex education.

The family planning program initiative by the government of India has shown improved results over the past few years and hope to steadily improve the results over time.

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